

Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action

#D6.1

Open Calls resolution report

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Executive summary

Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action (CoAct) is a Horizon 2020 project which aims to provide and further develop methodologies supporting an understanding of research that can equally be led by academic researchers or citizen groups. As part of that process, CoAct aims to support the United Nations fifth Sustainable Development Goal on gender equality by supporting civic organizations making use of CSS methods for gender-based projects. In this document, we set out a resolution report of the Open Call “Gender Equality”, which application process opened on the 1st of July 2021 and ended on the 30th September 2021.

We present first the course of the planning process of the Open Calls as discussed within the CoAct consortium; second the Open Calls processes itself; third an overview of the applications and selected grantees; fourth, we present our communication strategy; and fifth open up for some critical self-reflections of the Open Call process and how to adjust the procedure towards transdisciplinary, transregional and transcultural Open Calls for the future. Therefore, this document might be of interest for individuals and organisations interested in carrying out their own open call, particularly in the areas of CSS and gender equality. Finally, we summarize the work done thus far and point out further activities which are planned for the remaining project time with the grantees.

Eventually, grantees were selected for each of the Open Calls on “Gender Equality”. Three projects ranging from the fields of women of Color empowerment, trans-gender and non-binary access to the labor market, and examining the challenges women face in Greece by having to work in a digital environment due to the current pandemic. These grantees recently started their projects under the assistance of a CoAct consortium advisor. Until September 2022, we will respectively guide each other through this process in order to present the project results in December 2022.

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1. Introduction

CoAct stands for Co-designing Citizen Social Science for collective action. It is a research project that explores the field of Citizen Social Science funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 873048). CoAct is a transdisciplinary collaboration of research institutions and civil society organisations. The consortium brings together experts from different disciplines and fields of practice, such as Participatory Action Research, Computational Social Science, Citizen Science, Research Policy and Development, Digital Transformation, Social Movement Studies and Participatory Development Communication. CoAct proposes a new understanding of Citizen Social Science (CSS) as participatory research co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups sharing a social concern. CoAct aims to provide and further develop methodologies supporting an understanding of research that can equally be led by academic researchers and citizen groups. Doing so, the project seeks to create an environment that provides a more equal "seat at the table" in process, which are oftentimes dominated by academic researchers. CoAct is running three Research and Innovation Actions (R&I Actions) in which citizens act as co-researchers, actively participating in all phases of the research, from the design to the interpretation of the results and their transformation into actions. In this line, the CoAct Open Call provides funding for citizen groups to lead their own research projects based on their research interests. Academic researchers accompany these projects by providing their expertise to counselling, mentoring and facilitating the citizens research and innovation actions.

We understand Citizen Social Science as participatory research co-designed or directly driven by citizen groups that share a particular social concern. In CoAct's R&I Actions citizens act as co-researchers throughout the entire research process and are recognized as in-the-field competent experts being equal actors in all phases. In the co-designed research, the citizens explore their lived experiences regarding the specific social concerns that motivate the research actions. In these R&I Actions, we focus on the topics of mental health care, youth employment and environmental justice

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and gender equality. Such an approach enables them to address pressing social issues from the bottom up, embedded in their social contexts. Co-designed research provides the foundation for socially robust evidence-based knowledge that strives for sustainable impact and social change.

CoAct's "Gender Equality" Open Calls seek to move the boundaries of research that is initiated by academic scientists towards citizen-led research. CoAct invites further actors to benefit from science projects and the expertise and competence represented in the consortium. To support civic organizations CoAct makes use of a full range of CSS methods and best practices applied in our projects. Civil society organizations are directly dealing with specific topics of social concerns and are mostly organized in their practices around these. Therefore, the Open Calls aims at supporting the work of everyday experts at the grassroots level to explore the opportunities and challenges of citizen-led research.

The series of three citizen-led research pilots that become initiated by the Open Calls is situated in the field of gender equality. Gender equality is an ongoing major societal topic that constantly affects our daily life. The United Nations highlight "Gender Equality" as the fifth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) and define it as follows: (1) End all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere; (2) Eliminate all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres, including trafficking and sexual and other types of exploitation. In CoAct, we take this definition of SDG 5 as the starting point for the Work Package 6 (WP6) Open Calls. However, we want to consider gender equality in a wider and inclusive manner, including the full range and diversity of identities and collectives, in particular the LGBTQ+ communities. All perspectives related to any perceived gender identity, including non-binary ones, were thus included in the implementation of WP6.

The COVID-19 pandemic has regarding gender politics clearly brought the strongly rooted traditional role patterns in our system to light again, particularly care work. Simultaneously, we are witnessing new manifestations and visibilities, and—at least in some locations—more attention from

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policy and society of the different feminist and LGBTQ+ movements. Their claim for equity appears in various forms, for example in huge demonstrations (300,000 people in Barcelona on women day on 8th of March of 2019), the #Metoo movement or also intersectional movements like Black Lives Matter. There is a vast variety of different attempts to tackle the social construction and structural embeddedness of gender inequality. Very diverse types of actors with very different intentions play a relevant role in these movements. Movements range from demands for a women's quota in decision making positions, to human rights movements against discrimination and violence, up to more radical transformative approaches that criticize the basic exclusionary foundations of capitalism reproducing gender inequality. From our perspective, Citizen Social Science can strengthen and support these powerful grassroots approaches. In our understanding of Citizen Social Science, citizens in vulnerable situations need to be at the centre of the research cycle and involved in defining the social issues which they are affected from. This way, unprecedented scientific data on gender inequalities could be collected, possibly leading to new scientific evidence-informed collective actions and policymaking. Therefore, the Open Call aims on civil society organizations to apply for a short-term grant over a funding period of 10 months to investigate issues with a Citizen Social Science approach.

This document ensembles a reflection of the WP6 activities that have been carried out in three Open Calls aiming to initiate citizen-led CSS projects for mutual learning and knowledge exchange at three locations: Germany (Open Call I - Berlin & Brandenburg), Eastern Europe (Open Call II), and Europe (Open Call III). The thematic topics that are corresponding with specific regional foci are:

- "Sustainable cities and communities", Berlin and Brandenburg Area, Germany
- "Decent work and economic growth", Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia)
- "Opportunities and risks of digitalization", across all EU countries.

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Consequently, applicants had to show the relevance of their project to both gender equality and the specific focus of the Open Call of their choice.

Gender Equality & Sustainable Cities and Communities

CSOs in Berlin & Brandenburg area

“Sustainable cities and communities” (SDG 11) addresses initiatives in the Berlin and Brandenburg region that aim for making cities inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable for all its inhabitants. Proposals should have examined gender inequalities in affordable housing and/or urban planning as well as projects that promotes social, economic, environmental sustainability through community building around the topic of gender equality in its broadest sense.

Eligibility criteria:

- Applicant should have been a non-profit organization
- The candidate organisation should have been registered in the Berlin and Brandenburg region

Gender Equality & Decent Work and Economic Growth

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CSOs in Eastern Europe

“Decent work and economic growth” (SDG 8) addresses organisations in Eastern Europe. Whereas women in the EU earn on average over 16% less per hour than men this figure is even higher in Eastern Europe Countries. Trans and intersexual and none-binary people are facing even harder forms of discrimination regarding their work opportunities (EC 2018).

Eligibility criteria:

- Applicant should have been a non-profit organization
- The candidate organisation should have been registered in one of the following countries: Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia.

Gender Equality & Opportunities and Risks of Digitalization

International CSOs in the EU

“Opportunities and risks of digitalization” is open to international civic organisations operating in the EU. It has been pointed out that digital spaces are gendered spaces which hinder for example the participation of young women and that gendered norms are exacerbated online (EIGE 2019). Proposals should address the issues related to gender inequalities in online spaces, due, in part, to issues such as the gender dynamics of online platforms and the exposure to online harassment.

Eligibility criteria:

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- Applicant should have been a non-profit organization
- The candidate organisation should have had operations in at least two European countries.
- The candidate organisation should have been registered in a member country of the European Union.

2. Summary of the Call Process

The CoAct consortium was launching three Open Calls to foster CSO-led Citizen Social Science projects on Gender Equality. Between July 1st and September 30th of 2021, any non-profit organisation registered in the eligible countries were entitled to apply. Prior to this, the involved CoAct members organized weekly meetings from January 2021 to October 2021, in order to facilitate the Open Call process. The taskforce operated in thematic areas: recruiting process, communication strategy, application review process, grantee activities, grantee communications, grantee onboarding, project evaluation and reporting. The necessary work was equally shared within the WP6 responsible organisations.

Eventually, we invited civil society initiatives to send us their project proposal for our cascading grants up to 20.000,- Euro to conduct their own Citizen Social Science research on Gender Quality. A maximum of four applicants could have been selected across all three Open Call topics. We welcomed applications from a full range of gender identity backgrounds, including feminist, LGBTQ+, non-binary and critical masculinity perspectives as a result of our discussion in the consortium to broaden the narrow SDG 5 definition that equals gender with femininity.

Alongside the funding by CoAct, the grantees will profit from dedicated activities, resources, and tools to set up and run the research project. CoAct will provide a research mentoring program. Furthermore, in collaborative workshops, the grantees will be supported to co-design and explore CSS tools and get assistance from the CoAct team to achieve their goals. CoAct will connect them

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to a community of people and initiatives, tackling similar challenges and contributing to common aims. They will have the opportunity to discuss your projects with the other grantees and, moreover, are invited to join CoAct's broader Citizen Social Science network.

The call is divided into five key phases: call definition, application solicitation, evaluation, selection and negotiation. Successful projects eventually join over the period of ten month the CoAct accelerator and receive funding and ongoing support from the CoAct consortium. The timeline of these phases of the call can be seen in figure 1:

Figure 1: Timeline and milestones of the open calls

The first source of information for potential applicants is the [CoAct website](#), with a page dedicated to the Open Call. The website serves as the entry point for the call and offers all the documents and information that an applicant needs for the application process, along with information to the upcoming events accompany the Open Calls. All information and documents were available in

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different languages: Besides English in Czech, German and Polish. Applicants were strongly advised to read the 'Guide for Applicants' prior to their application (see Appendix A). This document contains all information regarding the Open Calls, including the aims of the call, eligibility, requirements, key dates and contact details for further questions.

CoAct's Open Calls invited: (A) ongoing Citizen Social Science projects looking for support, funding and other resources to grow and become sustainable; (B) affected communities interested in co-designing research to generate new knowledge about gender equality topics; and (C) non-profit organizations (in the third sectors) focussing on community building, increasing their visibility, strengthening civic participation or the exploration of application scenarios and the usability of Citizen Social Science in their work. The Open Call targeted groups were:

Applicants were required to be a legal non-profit entity in a country or territory eligible to receive Horizon 2020 grants. As a consequence, only organizations legally registered and operating in an EU member state or associated country are eligible for funding from CoAct. We encouraged consortia of different organisations to apply for our Open Calls. Each participant of a consortia must be eligible. And every consortia need to choose a project lead, which submit the application and engage (communicate) with CoAct on behalf of the consortium. Every entity is allowed to participate in only one application, either on its own or as part of a consortium as described above.

CoAct has the following conflict of interest policy: Immediate family, domestic and non-domestic partners and those with financial ties to members of the CoAct consortium members are prohibited to apply. If potential applicants have had a prior relationship with anyone contributing to CoAct that may constitute a conflict of interest, they were encouraged to reach out to the CoAct team for clarification.

Applicants were asked to complete an online form on the Open Call page of the CoAct website in order to apply for one of these calls. The online form was created by the CoAct team based on the

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project idea, anticipated impact, ethics and safety (see Table 1). The thematic areas, sub-topics and questions are presented in the following table.

Idea	Relevance to the call	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the proposal match the focus of the specific call it was submitted to? • Does it include activities compatible with Citizen Social Science?
	Project design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are the planned activities realistic given the proposed budget and time constraints? • Does the scope and complexity of the project match the profiles of the project’s team?
Impact	Link to a broader agenda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the project linked to a broader agenda/programme carried out by the applicant? • Does the project have a chance to continue beyond the length of the programme? • Is the idea reusable by other organizations working on similar topics? • Does the project present a participatory evaluation and impact assessment strategy?
	Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project consider the structural contribution of the issue at stake it aims to tackle/the community it aims to serve, beyond the timebound framing of this open call

	Documentation & Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which documentation strategies are planned? Is there a commitment to publish the data and results? • Where would the results of the projects be disseminated?
Ethics and Safety	Ethical considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there any ethical considerations relevant to the project, and if so, how are they taken into account? • Is there a clear commitment to data protection and anonymization where relevant? • How does the applicant plan to ensure that their activities are as inclusive as possible?
	Health & Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the project requires physical meetings, what processes are put in place to protect the health of participants in the contest of the Covid19 pandemic?

Table 1: Review themes

The selected items of the online form were then re-evaluated and linked to their value for CSS research (see Table 2). The applicants had to describe their project proposal but also a series of questions about their eligibility, and their ability to conduct the research project. Only complete applications that were submitted before the deadline were considered for review. All information was required to be in English. In addition to the questions within the template, we produced a public set of criteria, broken down according to the main principles we would expect in a successful application, each with a set of questions.

Value for CSS research

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Relevance to the call	Identifies if the project clearly tackles a Social Science related issue at stake and if it is explicitly based on citizen ownership or significant participation.
Project design	Is the proposed activity feasible to be completed in the given timeframe? What are the resources required (internal and external capacities, capacity building, technologies, etc.) and how are they addressed in the project plan?
Link to a broader agenda	Identifies if the project is viable beyond this specific grant.
Sustainability	Structural contribution to CSS, growing the approach and or serving other communities/projects and use of proprietary versus free and open sources software / building new tools versus adapting existing tools.
Documentation & Dissemination	Identifies if the project's outputs can be properly documented for analysis and dissemination purposes.
Ethical considerations	Identifies if the project matches with the standard ethical principles of CSS research

Table 2: Review themes and their value for CSS

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Eligible applications were then reviewed by the CoAct team and external reviewers with academic background in CSS. The external reviewers were selected academics with expertise in the field of gender inequality and regional foci regarding Call I and Call II. None of the internal nor external reviewers stated conflicts of interest regarding the selection process.

Before that, we research each individual applicant’s online presence to check if it matches with the information they gave. Additionally, we reached out to the organization to confirm that they are associated with the person who applied in their name. After this background check, the reviewers were asked to rate the application accordingly to our reviewer guideline and its proposed criteria (see Table 3). Reviewers were asked to make overall comments, as well as comments on the idea, impact, and implementation. Each eligible applicant received a copy of these reviews after the completion of the review process.

Criteria/Themes	Relevant questions in the questioner	Review guidance
Relevance to the Open Call	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please describe in a few sentences what your proposal aims to achieve • Please explain the relevance of your proposal to gender equality issues and Citizen Social Science • Please list the goals of your project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the description match the theme of the call? Is the proposal clearly rooted in advancing Gender Equality? • Is the proposal explicitly contributing to shaping CSS?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In what ways does your project or its results benefit the communities you are part of? 	
Project design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please list the goals of your project • Please list the activities planned in order to address these goals? • What (technical, human) resources are necessary in order to enact those activities? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the applicant have an explicit strategic agenda? • Do the activities match the envisioned goals? • Does the applicant have sufficient capacities or a realistic planning and budgeting for additionally required capacities?
Links to a broader agenda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please describe the main activities of your organization • How does the proposed project relate to the overall mission or programmatic agenda of your organisation/coalition? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project appear to be connected to the broader mission of the organisation? • Is their explanation about the added value of the project convincing?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will this project support the advancement of your organisation’s overall agenda? If so, how? 	
Documentation and Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do you plan to document your project’s progress? • How and to which audiences do you plan to disseminate the results of your project? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three elements to look out for: administrative documentation (reports), internal documentation (meeting notes etc.), and external documentation (blog posts etc.)
Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How and to which audiences do you plan to disseminate the results of your project? • In what ways does your project or its results benefit the communities you are part of? • Are you planning to use software tools or 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does it look like the project will be able to continue after the CoAct funding ends?

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	<p>resources to deliver your project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If yes, do you expect this software to be open source? If yes, will you develop the software yourself or do you plan to adapt existing tools? 	
Ethical considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does your project present potential ethical issue? If so, please list them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is their assessment of the ethical issues of their project convincing?
Covid measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If your project presents a health risk in the context of the COVID pandemic, please state your plan to mitigate the risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do the Covid measures appear sufficient / in-line with the commonly accept measure of prevention?

Table 3: Guidance for the reviewers

The applicants with best rated projects were included in a shortlist and invited for a remote interview. Based on the reviews, the CoAct team created internal briefing documents on selected grantees prior to the interviews. We anticipated interviews to be held between 6th and 8th October 2021. Each interview was set for 45 minutes with 15 additional minutes of jury discussions. The interview took place on Google Meet. The goal of the interview was to get a better understanding of the applicant’s organisation, project proposal and compatibility with the CoAct programme. The

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interviews started with a presentation of their project by the applicant, followed by a discussion with jury members about topics that needed a clarification.

The selection process was followed by a negotiation process during which due diligence checks were done and a workshop was organised. During these workshops the selected applicants worked with the CoAct team to address any identified issue with their roadmap, timeline and deliverables before adding them as an annex to the contract. The initial timeline of this process is outlined below:

1 st July 2021 – 30 th September 2021	Open Call’s application window
6 th – 8 th October 2021	Interview of shortlisted applicants
11 th – 22 nd October 2021	Negotiation process
25 th – 26 th October	Planning Workshop
1 st November 2021 – 31 st August 2022	Project Time
December 2022	Final Presentation

Table 4: Initial milestones of the Open Call “Gender Equality”:

These milestones, however, had to be adjusted. Due to recruiting two external reviewers and them not completing their reviews within the expected timeline, the review process was delayed. Thus, the interview process lasted until the last week of October and the negotiation process went until the end of November. In addition, a key member of the WP6 team being temporarily removed from the project due to health issues, the negotiation process was slowed down. The start the project planning work – which marks the start of the projects – parallel to the negotiation process in mid-November. Eventually, the teams will be able to deliver their final reports in September 2022 instead of August 2022.

Beyond this, the structure of the call and major milestones will remain the same, following the presentation of the project outcomes to be introduced by CoAct in December 2022.

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3. Call Statistics

For the Open Calls, we received 15 applications in total. All 15 application were reviewed and evaluated. A breakdown of evaluation outcomes can be seen in Table 1 below.

Call No.	No. of applicants
I	4
II	4
II	7

Table 5: Call Statistics

For the first call, we received applications from Berlin, even though the call was also located in Brandenburg, a federal state next to Berlin. The second call attracted three organisations in Sofia, Bulgaria, and one from Zvolen (Slovakia). The third call had the most diverse range of locations, as expected for the European call, with one applicant from Den Haag, Netherlands, two from Athens, Greece, one from Barcelona, Spain, and two from Italy, Rome and Genoa.

All organizations show strong expertise in the field of gender equality. The detailed proposal themes were education, civic dialog, refugee support, economic gender mainstreaming, anti-discrimination work, LGBTQ+ empowerment, lobbying, city transformation, and women advocacy.

3.1. Evaluation Outcomes

Three non-profit organizations were selected to be grantees as part of the CoAct Open Calls for gender equality:

Open Call	Grantee	Webpage	Project outline
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1	Founderland	www.founderland.org	<p>Less than 0.5% of venture capital goes to women of colour founders. Their proposal aims to unearth the structural and systemic challenges for women of colour founders in Berlin face when it comes to company formation and investment (including VC, government grants and other financial instruments).</p> <p>At Founderland, they define women of colour, as women who have faced obstacles due to their race/ethnicity/gender in their entrepreneurial journey. Founderland will generate the first comprehensive report on the state of entrepreneurship in this region through the intersectional lens of gender, race and ethnicity.</p>
2	Single Step	www.singlestep.bg/en/	<p>Their proposal aims to achieve better visibility of trans and non-binary people both in research work and on the labour market through a</p>

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			<p>comprehensive methodology to measure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Quality of life of trans and non-binary people in relation to access to the labour market and at the work place. To be measured with a standardized open access questionnaire PHQ-9.• Generalized anxiety, related to poor access to employment opportunities or related to personal experience at the workplace. Measured with a standardized open access questionnaire GAD-7.• Correlation between (1) level of education, (2) employment status and opportunities and (3) economic status.• Specific HR questionnaires: Evaluation of quality of employment and integration
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			<p>(targeted at employed non-binary and trans individuals), evaluation of level of employment opportunities (targeted at job seekers from target group), evaluation of equal opportunity and employment protection (targeted at employers).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The economic value lost by not having equal access of trans and non-binary people to the labor market: the opportunity cost of not hiring the person most qualified for the position.
3	Women on Top	www.womenontop.gr/en/	<p>The aim of this research project is to assess the current realities, threats and opportunities facing women in Greece who were forced or chose to move to a remote mode of work, learning and networking, mainly due to the COVID pandemic.</p>

			<p>By analysing, synthesizing and disseminating the collected quantitative and qualitative data, Women on Top aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Create public awareness around opportunities (accessibility, work life balance etc.) & threats (digital skills gap, limited development opportunities, cyber harassment etc.) for women in the public sphere.• Build capacity in corporate and learning environments to leverage opportunities and mitigate threats.• Create policy recommendations around issues such as cyber harassment and the digital skills gap.• Build training curricula and other tools to support women and organisations in adapting to this ever-
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			changing workplace environment.
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Table 6: Selected grantees

Before the formal start of their research activities, several steps were necessary:

- writing and signing the contract (Admin onboarding)
- working out a coordination strategy (Coordination planning)
- refining their project plan (Project design support)
- providing scientific advice from the consortium partner to make use of best practices in Citizen Social Science (Scientific support)
- reviewing the working plan from a Monitoring & Evaluation angle (M&E support)
- identifying capacity building needs (Learning plan)
- planning communication activities (Communication support)

4. Relationship with Applicants and Communication Strategy

Before launching the Open Calls, the members of the WP6 taskforce responsible for our capacity building conceptualized a communication strategy. This resulted in a communication package including blog posts templates, example tweets, and email templates in English and German. Prior to the opening of the call, a communication document with links to various resources, such as contact addresses of potential organisations of interest (such as universities, CSS groups) and media, was created. This was then used to distribute press statements and the Open Calls itself.

On launching the Open Call on July 1st, 2021, the CoAct team published the Open Call on their website. The website itself advertised the Open Call with a signified tab on top of every page on the website that indicates the possibility to apply for the Open Call. Additionally, a frequently asked questions section was provided for applicants on the CoAct website. It covers questions such as

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about the eligibility criteria for each call. Furthermore, CoAct managed a signal chat group and twitter page for interested actors and individuals within the Citizen Social Science community. This network was asked to distribute the Open Call in their lists. Additionally, all members of the consortium supported the distribution of the Open Calls in their networks. At the same time, the consortium highlighted the danger of potential conflicts of interest regarding of applications from individuals related on different levels with members of the consortium. Furthermore, the CoAct team established a potential bias and remediation strategy. In this, we have reflected on the use of language as potential barrier and bias, and possible advantages bigger NGOs might have in our application process in contrast to organizations with no legal status.

4.1. Personal Consultation

The CoAct launched an email helpline for potential applicants (opencall@coactproject.eu) to request information to ask questions. The helpline was managed by members of the consortium and aimed to response to applicants within a few days wherever possible. Potential applicants reached out to our helpline with questions such as if their project meets the criteria of our Open Call.

Besides contact via email, we also encouraged potential applicants to participate in CoAct webinars on gender equality and our monthly online hangouts on gender related topics in order to providing the space for advice. The webinars and hangouts target individual and groups working on the subject of gender equality to contribute with their experiences, projects, or research in the CSS community.

4.2. Q&A Session

During the Open Call, the CoAct team organized two Q&A Sessions for potential applicants - one in August and one in September. Interested applicants had to register prior to the Q&A Sessions

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via email before they received an invitation link to the conference platform that CoAct used at that time. Besides interested applicants, the Q&A Sessions were visited by eventually misogynistic and sexist trolls who bombed the Q&A Session. During the Covid-19 pandemic, practices like so-called “Zoombombing” increased drastically. In a Zoombombing incident, especially misogynistic, homophobic, and racist trolls and incels hijack specific teleconferences that aim to empower marginalized groups. Even though our security actions were level upped after the first incident, trolls again tried to hijack the second Q&A Session. On both incidences, we managed to keep the control of the event and act on these happenings with reasonable interventions. These experiences do not only highlight the vulnerability of gender related project, but also the need of empowerment and support of these projects such as the Open Call “Gender Equality”.

5. Critical Reflexion

For the selection process of the Open Call on “Gender Equality”, the objectives, procedures and tools used were generally successful. We received 15 applications, with a variety of gender related focuses, citizen activities and countries of origin. We note that some areas of in the application and on-boarding process must be improved:

- Legal and bureaucratic requirements were too high. We did not reach as many organizations, especially grass-roots movements, and groups, as we anticipated. One reason could be that the eligibility criteria of being a legal non-profit entity within the EU were too restrictive for social movements and communities without any formal organization structure.
- Some applicants struggled to understand that the proposal must fit to the given framework set by the Sustainable Development Goals. Some applicants did not frame their proposal adequately. Especially a description of the overall goals of the project were missing, instead the project was explained in terms of the planned activities.

To address these issues, we propose three major changes for future calls:

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- There is a need for less formal requirements and a more bottom-up approach regarding the legal eligibility, in particular for applicants outside of solfaed structures. This may not only increase the overall number of applicants, but furthermore support and empower less privileged actor of civic society.
- A more concrete and practical guide for applicants is necessary that clarifies the thematic framework of each Call by providing examples.

In addition to these changes necessitated by administrative and conceptional issues, we noted several improvable steps throughout the Open Call process:

- Having three Open Calls targeting respectively Germany, Eastern Europe, and all other member state of the European Union, we critically discussed the languages chosen to provide information and documentation. The application guide was only translated into Czech, German and Polish. For all other countries, English served as the lingua franca. This circumstance disadvantages especially grass-root organizations and non-formal civic society actors without sufficient knowledge or access to one of the languages mentioned above. In addition to the legal requirements – which might have been a barrier for potential applicants with no recognized legal status or structure –, this constitutes a hard to achieve eligibility for applicants who did not undergo academic education.,
- On top, all applicants were required to hand in all documents in English. This not only demanded very good command on language skills or investments into translations but might let to barriers and disadvantages for applicants for whom English was not first language or were not able to develop enough proficiency. also weakened the proposal on a conceptional level as English was not the first language of all applicants.
- Drawing from transregional perspectives within our consortium, we were able to adjust our Open Call to cultural demands in regards of advertising and contextualization. However, the consortium lacks project partners from eastern European states. Even though we provided translation in Czech and Polish, the Open Call II received no applications from the Czech

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Republic or Poland, but instead from Bulgaria and Slovakia. For similar calls in the future, it might be crucial to eventually cultivate contacts within the region of their anticipated Calls and their respected needs.

- To include a younger generation and more diverse range of civic society actors, future projects might consider focusing their advertisement outside of established communication channels within academia and other conventional fields (e.g. working with influential actors on social media channels in order to promote the call to activists in different fields). Therefore, we highly recommend working with advertisement experts to improve the communication strategies and distribution of future calls.
- As the Open Call „Gender Equality” pushes three calls in one, the consortium aimed to centralize as many tasks as possible in order to minimize the overall workload. This could be improved, if administrative tasks were simplified by for example providing template contracts by the European administration.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

We assess the Open Calls as a success despite these critical points of reflexions of the application and selection process. We found three promising candidates not only for contributing to social science research fields from a genuine citizen perspective but also to discuss and invent new ways to extend the contributions of citizens for social science and for a democratization of science. The ambition is to extend the possibilities of Citizen Social Science methodology towards citizen-led projects. and to explore new ways for deep participation. To guide our grantees through their projects, we decided to establish a supervisory relationship – and at the same time, to honour and secure the autonomy and integrity of these projects. We particularly assist our grantees to cope with the bureaucratic demands and offer scientific training and guidance for a successful research project. Furthermore, we support our grantees to carry out all activities entirely online, without a

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need for events that must be attended physically in person if the Corona epidemic will become server again throughout Europe.

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Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action

APPLICANTS GUIDE TO OPEN CALLS “GENDER EQUALITY”

1 July 2021

The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 873048

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Introduction

On **1 July 2021 (12am GMT)** CoAct is launching a call for proposals, inviting civil society initiatives to apply for our cascading grants for citizen-led Citizen Social Science research on the topic of "Gender equality". A maximum of four (4) applicants will be selected across three (3) different open calls. This document provides a guide to support civil society initiatives participating in the call and preparing their submission. The guide constitutes the main source of information for the calls. In case of factual conflicts with other sources of information (such as the CoAct website), the contents of this guide are deemed authoritative. Should you have any outstanding queries regarding the application procedure after reading this document, please refer to the [FAQ](#) on our website or contact us at opencalls@coactproject.eu.

What is CoAct?

CoAct stands for Co-designing Citizen Social Science for collective action. It is a research project that explores the field of Citizen Social Science funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 873048). It proposes a new understanding of Citizen Social Science (CSS) as participatory research co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups sharing a social concern. CoAct aims to provide and further develop methodologies supporting an understanding of research that can equally be led by academic researchers or citizen groups. Doing so, the project seeks to create an environment that provides a more equal "seat at the table" in process, which are oftentimes dominated by academic researchers. CoAct is running three so called Research and Innovation Actions (R&I Actions) in which citizens act as co-researchers, actively participating in all phases of the research, from the design to the interpretation of the results and their transformation into concrete actions. Simultaneously, with the CoAct Open Calls provide funding for citizen groups to lead their own participatory research, inviting academic researchers in.

What is Citizen Social Science?

We understand Citizen Social Science as participatory research co-designed or directly driven by citizen groups that share a particular social concern. In CoAct's R&I Actions citizens act as co-researchers throughout the entire research process and are recognized as in-the-field competent experts being equal actors in all phases. In the co-designed research, the citizens explore their lived experience regarding the specific social concerns that motivate the research actions. In these R&I Actions, we focus on the topics of mental health care, youth employment and environmental justice and gender equality. Such an approach enables to address pressing social issues from the bottom up, embedded in their social contexts. Co-designed research provides the foundation for socially robust evidence-based knowledge that strives for sustainable impact and social change.

Why a CoAct Open Call?

CoAct's Open Call seeks to move beyond its own co-research activities and invite further actors to benefit from the project and its support mechanisms. We want to support civic organizations in making use of CSS methods and best practices in their own projects, directly from within civil society. Civil society organizations are directly dealing with specific social topics of concern and are mostly organized around these. Therefore, the CoAct Open Calls seeks to connect to expert work at the grassroots level to explore the opportunities and challenges of citizen-led research.

Why an open call on Gender Equality?

Gender equality is an ongoing major societal topic that constantly affects our daily life. The United Nations made "Gender Equality" the fifth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) and define it as follows: (1) End all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere; (2) Eliminate all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres, including trafficking and sexual and other types of exploitation. In CoAct, we take SDG5 as the starting point for this Open call but we want to consider gender equality in a wider and inclusive manner, including all perspectives

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and collectives, such as by addressing all perspectives, such as LGBTQ+, non-binary and critical masculinity.

The COVID-19 pandemic has clearly brought the strongly rooted traditional role patterns in our system to light again, particularly regarding care work. Simultaneously, we are witnessing new manifestations and visibilities, and—at least in some locations—more attention from policy and society of the different feminist and LGBTQ+ movements with claims for equity appearing in various forms, for example in huge demonstrations (300,000 people in Barcelona on 8th of March of 2019), the #Me too!-movement or also intersectional movements like Black Lives Matter. There is a vast variety of different attempts to tackle the social construction and structural embeddedness of gender inequality and many types of actors can play a relevant role. Movements range from demands for a women's quota in decision making positions, to human rights movements against discrimination and violence up to more radical transformative approaches that criticize the basic exclusionary foundations of capitalism.

From our perspective, Citizen Social Science can provide a powerful grassroots approach to this global issue. In our understanding of Citizen Social Science, citizens in vulnerable situations need to be at the centre of the research cycle, defining the focus on a specific social issue. This way, unprecedented scientific data related to gender inequalities could be collected, possibly leading to new scientific evidence-informed reactions and the proposal of new collective actions or policy making.

Therefore, we want to invite civil society organizations to apply for a short-term grant to investigate issues with a Citizen Social Science approach. Funded projects will receive financial backing as well as support via mentoring by CoAct consortium partners, including academic researchers, global networks, NGOs and others.

Topics of the Open Calls on Gender Equality

Taking into account the broad field of topics related to gender equality we decided to focus on particular topics that would serve the United Nations sustainable development goals (SDGs).

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Applications have to be clearly related to gender equality, understood widely as described previously, and one of the three thematic and regional foci:

(1) Sustainable cities and communities

The first Open Call “Sustainable cities and communities” (SDG 11) is addressing initiatives in the Berlin and Brandenburg region that aim for making cities inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable for all its inhabitants ([UN 2020](#)). Proposals should examine gender inequalities in affordable housing and/or urban planning as well as projects that promotes social, economic, environmental sustainability through community building around the topic of gender equality in its broadest sense.

(2) Decent work and economic growth

The second Open Call “Decent work and economic growth” (SDG 8) is addressing organisations in Eastern Europe. Whereas women in the EU earn on average over 16% less per hour than men this figure becomes is even higher in Eastern Europe Countries ([EIGE 2015](#)). Trans and intersexual and non-binary people are facing even harder forms of discrimination regarding their work opportunities ([EC 2018](#)). Organisations from Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia are invited to submit a proposal.

(3) Opportunities and risks of digitalization

The third Open Call “Opportunities and risks of digitalization” is open to international civic organisations operating in the EU. It has been pointed out that digital spaces are gendered spaces which hinder for example the participation of young women and that digital norms are exacerbated online ([EIGE 2019](#)). Proposals should address the issues related to gender inequalities in online spaces, due, in part, to issues such as the gender dynamics of online platforms and the exposure to online harassment.

Why take part?

- CoAct will provide **funding for a research project (10 months max)**, alongside dedicated activities, resources and tools to set up and run the research project.
- CoAct will provide a research **mentoring program** for your team. In collaborative workshops you will be supported to co-design and explore available tools working together with the CoAct team to achieve your goals.
- CoAct will **connect** you to a community of people and initiatives, tackling similar challenges and contributing to common aims. You will have the opportunity to discuss your projects with the other grantees and moreover are invited to join CoAct's broader Citizen Social Science network.

Who is the funding for?

CoAct's Open Calls are inviting:

- ongoing Citizen Social Science projects looking for support, financial and otherwise, to grow and become sustainable;
- communities interested in co-designing research to generate new knowledge about gender equality topics;
- organizations in the third sectors that focus on community building, increasing the visibility of specific communities, increasing civic participation and who are interested in exploring the use of Citizen Social Science in their work.

The funding is available to legal entities and consortia established in a country or territory eligible to receive Horizon 2020 grants. Only organizations legally registered and operating in an EU member state or associated country are eligible for funding from CoAct. For consortia of different organisations, all participants must be eligible. In this case, the participants also need to choose a research project lead, which will submit the application and engage with CoAct on behalf of the consortium.

Every entity is allowed to participate, either on its own or as part of a consortium as described above.

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CoAct has the following conflict of interest policy: Immediate family, domestic and non-domestic partners and those with financial ties to members of the CoAct consortium members are prohibited to apply. If you have a prior relationship with anyone contributing to CoAct that you feel may constitute a conflict of interest, please email opencalls@coactproject.eu for clarification.

What is the funding for?

The funding will be set at a maximum of 20,000,- Euro for Call 1 and 3, for which only one applicant will be selected. Call 2 will select two proposals, which will share the 20,000,- Euro grant, with a maximum of 15,000,- Euro for a single organisation. The funding can be spent on salaries, equipment, consumables, travel, subcontracting to other entities, and indirect expenditure (calculated as 25% of the total direct costs, see [Annex 1](#)), in accordance with [Horizon 2020 guidelines](#).

In your application, you will be asked to describe your effort and the resources you plan to mobilize for this amount. You may propose any cost items deemed eligible and relevant for the delivery of your research project. See [Annex 2](#) of this document for further explanation.

The activities you plan to carry out with CoAct cannot receive double funding. Synergies with other sources of funding, including other Horizon 2020 projects, are encouraged as long as the grants are used for complementary, not overlapping purposes.

Who keeps the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)?

By default you will be the sole owner of the results and outcomes of your project, and all associated intellectual property. You can decide however upon ownership within your teams and among the involved parties but applicants should be using a Creative Commons license when publishing results.

However, we expect all proposals to follow an open approach, sharing results and experiences widely with the community, as in any EU project. We will give priority to those applications that have a well-articulated plan for this.

In addition, CoAct or the European Commission may ask you to present your work as part of our public relations and networking events, in order to showcase and discuss the benefits and challenges of the CoAct approach.

What happens with the data?

Applicants will have to be clear in the application about the data that they expect to collect, generate and manage through the project. The processing of that data should be in compliance with the general data protection regulation (GDPR). As noted earlier, **we will only accept proposals that are committed to making their data, methods and outputs publicly available for reuse**, following an open science approach. For that CoAct will provide technical, legal and operational support to successful applicants.

In addition, CoAct will require Citizen Social Science projects funded through the programme to collect, manage and share data with and for the CoAct team for co-evaluation purposes. The specifics of the data to be collected will be defined with each project team.

How is the CoAct Open Call organized?

There are three different Open Calls, each with a different thematic and regional focus. In total, a maximum of four (4) grassroots gender equality research projects will be selected to receive a grant. This document refers to all three CoAct Open Call topics and regional foci.

Topics and regional foci

CoAct supports Citizen Social Science efforts tackling gender inequalities. This includes, but is not limited to, initiatives generating awareness of gender inequalities, facilitating new knowledge about its causes and consequences, and implementing measures towards reaching gender equality.

As noted earlier, our understanding of Citizen Social Science is broad and inclusive. We are seeking to fund ideas that can make a difference, at a local and an international scale. We are particularly interested in applications that propose novel, less explored participatory roles for citizens and other

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key stakeholders. We are looking forward to receiving applications that engage with groups that are considered marginalized, underrepresented or disadvantaged.

While all three Open Calls have a focus on gender equality, each call has a specific secondary focus:

- (1) “Sustainable cities and communities”, Berlin and Brandenburg Area, Germany
- (2) “Decent work and economic growth”, Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia)
- (3) “Opportunities and risks of digitalization”, across all EU countries.

Consequently, applicants will have to show the relevance of their project to both gender equality and the specific focus of the Open Call of their choice. It is possible for one organization to apply to several Open Calls, for different projects.

In response to ongoing challenges (e.g. health & safety, travel restrictions), all applicants will be required to explain how their projects can be carried out safely throughout the 10 months of the programme. Planned offline interactions need to ensure that all precautions are taken in accordance to local regulations and safety best practices.

Application process

Submission is done online via a [Google Form](#) available on the Open Calls page of the CoAct website. Applicants will be asked to describe their project proposal but also a series of questions about their eligibility to apply for funding, and their ability to conduct the research project.

Only complete applications submitted before the deadline will be considered for review. All information provided must be in English.

The applications will be reviewed by the CoAct team with the help of external reviewers with expertise on the difference focus topics. The applicants with best rated projects (see Annex for criteria list) will be included in a shortlist and proposed a date for a remote interview. We anticipate interviews to be held between 6th and 8th October 2021. Successful candidates will receive technical and financial support from the CoAct team over the ten months of the project.

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The selection process will be followed by a negotiation process during which due diligence checks will be done and a workshop will be organised. During the workshop selected applicants will work with the CoAct team to address any identified issue with their roadmap, timeline and deliverables before adding them as an annex to the contract. The timeline of this process is outlined below:

1 st July 2021 – 30 th September 2021	Open Call’s application window
6 th – 8 th October 2021	Interviews of shortlisted applicants
11 th – 22 nd October 2021	Negotiation process
25 th – 26 th October 2021	Planning Workshop
1 st November 2021 – 31 st August 2022	Project Time
December 2022	Final Presentation

How to apply?

1. The starting point for your application is the CoAct website. Go to the [application website](#).
2. Read this guide, as well as the [FAQ](#) and related tutorials available on that page.
3. Click on the ‘Submit application’ link and fill the form.
4. Make sure to answer all questions and upload all relevant documents. These documents are:
 - a. A legal document of incorporation
 - b. A declaration of honour dated and signed. A copy is available in [Annex 4](#) or at link to [application website](#).
5. After clicking on ‘Submit’, you will still be able to edit your application. Your final submission must be done before the **deadline: 30 September 2021, 12AM (GMT)**.

How do we select proposals?

Step 1 – Eligibility checks

CoAct checks if eligibility criteria are met. Proposals considered not eligible will not proceed to Step 2. The criteria are listed under “Who is the funding for?” in this document.

Step 2 – Reviews and shortlist

Eligible proposals will be evaluated by at least two reviewers against the following criteria:

1. Idea
2. Impact
3. Ethics & Safety.

Reviewers will evaluate each answer individually, on a 3-point scale and will also provide recommendations to shortlist the applications. The criteria we will follow are available in [Annex 4](#) of this document. Consider them when answering the questions from the short proposal.

Step 3 – Interview

Shortlisted applicants will be invited to a remote interview with an expert panel. The interview will consist of a short pitch of the application, followed by questions. We operate on a very tight schedule and the interviews will all be booked between 6th and 8th October 2021. Shortlisted candidates will be proposed several interview slot options in order to make it possible for everyone to attend. If none of the slots are possible for the applicant, we will be forced to reject the application.

Applicants who were not shortlisted will be informed at this stage as well.

Step 4 – Decisions

After the interview, the panel will decide whether to accept the applicant into the programme. We will provide feedback to applicants to improve their project. Unfortunately, due to the high number of applications anticipated, we will have a very limited capacity to reply to any queries on unsuccessful

applications. Decisions will be final and cannot be contested. We plan to inform applicants about the outcome latest by 15th October 2021.

Step 5 – Negotiation

If your application is successful, you will join the negotiation phase, which will conclude with the signature of a contract between your organization and the CoAct Consortium member overseeing the Open Call you applied to. For this to happen, we will have to complete the following steps:

- Due diligence checks: these checks are performed to understand the status of the applicant. We will check your legal entity information, ethics requirements, financial information and any other checks as requested by the European Commission before commencing the project. Should you fail the due diligence checks, CoAct reserves the right to reject the application.
- Workplan and budget agreement: a workshop will be organized before the formal start of the project to help improve your project plan and come up with agreed upon milestones, outcomes assessment process and success criteria. We will also evaluate the costs associated with your project to ensure they are realistic under the grant. This process will lead to the signature of the contract. You will be assigned an advisor who will go through this process with you and answer any questions.

The negotiation phase will start 11th October 2021 and will conclude 22nd October 2021, with a signed contract (see [Annex 5](#)). You will receive two payments—one at the beginning of the project and a second one when the CoAct team has reviewed the interim project report after the first five month.

Step 6 – CoAct facilitation

Applicants who reach this stage of the process are formally accepted into the ten-month project facilitation between 1st November 2021 and 31st August 2022.

The CoAct team will provide selected projects with resources and support, tailored to the needs of each project, including:

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- a two-day planning workshop at the end of the negotiation process, where we will discuss topics such as project design, diversity and inclusion, citizen engagement, data management and preservation, sustainability and impact assessment;
- online mentoring during the whole project;
- tools and infrastructure to host projects and their data according to state-of-the-art IT practices;
- tools and methods to facilitate participatory data collection and analysis;
- consultancy on a diverse set of citizen science challenges, including: data quality, data preservation, GDPR, research ethics, motivating participation, citizen empowerment, EDI (equality, diversity, inclusion), public engagement, and impact;
- promotion on our communication channels such as the CoAct web site and social media, as well as speaking opportunities at the CoAct “Gender Equality” event to present the outcome of the research and other related events;
- peer learning and networking facilitated through workshops and online tools.
- webinars on relevant topics

Participation in the facilitation activities provided by CoAct are a requirement for receiving the funding. The specific planning of those activities will be discussed with selected applicants during the planning workshop. Funds will be transferred in two stages—50% at the beginning of the project, and the remaining 50% at the end with the completion of activities outlined below:

- Attend training, webinars, and co-design workshops (as agreed during the planning workshop);
- Attend monthly update calls with mentors and / or other projects;
- Produce a mid-term and a final report outlining your activities at the end of the research project;
- Provide a short video about your work to be shared on the CoAct website;
- Participate in CoAct co-evaluation activities, such as

- citizen scientists feedback exercises
- defining and co-creating Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

Attend an in-depth self-assessment interview close to project completion

Present project achievements at the CoAct final conference. The conference will take place December 2022, with an audience made of practitioners, researchers, decision makers and representatives of the European Commission.

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Annexes

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Annex 1: Eligible costs

Overview

CoAct's grant is provided by Horizon 2020, a large research and innovation programme funded by the European Commission. As such, CoAct and the Citizen Social Science projects it supports need to ensure the funds are spent in accordance to Horizon 2020 guidelines. The following provides a summary of these guidelines. Please get in touch at opencalls@coactproject.eu if you have any questions.

The 20,000,- Euro grant may be spent only on eligible costs. These are costs that meet the following criteria:

- Incurred by the applicant in connection with or during the project;
- Identifiable and verifiable in the applicant's accounts;
- Compliant with national law;
- Reasonable, justified, in accordance with sound financial management (economy and efficiency);
- Indicated in the budget you submitted with the short proposal.

CoAct will provide training and guidance to all funded projects on financial matters.

Cost categories and reimbursement guidelines

The budget you submit will have to include different cost categories, which are explained below. There is a general distinction between **direct costs**, **subcontracting**, and **indirect costs** (also known as overheads). Indirect costs are calculated at 25% of the direct costs; no indirect costs can be charged on subcontracting. All costs, except for purchased equipment (see below), can be booked to the project's budget covered by the grant. Indirect costs, which are charged on top of the total direct costs, should be included. All costs should be stated inclusive of any irrecoverable VAT.

Direct costs: Personnel (100% reimbursed + indirect costs)

Applicants can spend CoAct funds on the staff directly involved in the execution of the project.

Direct costs: Equipment (15% reimbursed + indirect costs)

Equipment with a useful life in excess of the project duration can only be reimbursed to the extent the asset would be depreciated for the ten-month project period. Therefore, the standard rate allowed under the contracted project will be 15% of the total costs of the asset for a ten-month period. Indirect costs can be applied to the 15% of costs charged to the project.

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The costs of equipment rental for the project period can be charged at full cost, as long as the rental cost is not greater than the depreciation cost had the equipment been purchased.

Direct costs: Consumables, other goods and services (100% reimbursed + indirect costs)

Applicants can spend on consumables and other goods and services (including travel), if they are directly relevant for the achievement of the project.

There is no hard-and-fast rule about the distinction between equipment and other costs; small items such as moderation cards may be budgeted as ‘other goods and services’.

Subcontracting (100% reimbursed, no indirect costs)

Applicants may subcontract some of their activities to other parties as long as they are also from a Horizon 2020 eligible country. No indirect costs (overhead) can be charged on subcontracting costs. Note that we expect the applicant to carry out most of the tasks of the project—subcontracting cannot be used to carry out key tasks in the project.

Indirect costs

Indirect costs are within the 20,000,- Euro or 15,000,- Euro limit and cover items such as rent, admin, printing, photocopying, amenities etc. These costs are eligible if they are declared on the basis of the flat rate of 25% of the eligible costs, from which are excluded:

- Costs of subcontracting and
- Costs of in-kind contributions provided by third parties which are not used on the applicant’s premises

Annex 2: Declaration of honour

1. I declare:

- a. the organization that I represent is not bankrupt or being wound up, is not having its affairs administered by the courts, has not entered into an arrangement with creditors, has not suspended business activities, is not the subject of proceedings concerning those matters, nor is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for in national legislation or regulations;
- b. neither the organization that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been convicted of an offence concerning their professional conduct by a judgment which has the force of res judicata;
- c. neither the organization that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been guilty of grave professional misconduct proven by any means which the contracting authority can justify including by decisions of the European Investment Bank and international organizations;
- d. the organization that I represent is in compliance with its obligations relating to the payment of social security contributions or the payment of taxes in accordance with the legal provisions of the country in which it is established or with those of the country of the contracting authority or those of the country where the contract is to be performed;
- e. neither the organization that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been the subject of a judgment which has the force of res judicata for fraud, corruption, involvement in a criminal organization or any other illegal activity, where such illegal activity is detrimental to the Union's financial interests;
- f. the organization that I represent is not subject to an administrative penalty for being guilty of misrepresenting the information required by the contracting authority as a condition of participation in a grant award procedure or another procurement procedure or failing to supply this information, or having been declared to be in serious breach of its obligations under contracts or grants covered by the Union's budget.

2. I declare that I:

- a. am not subject to a conflict of interest;
- b. have not made false declarations in supplying the information required by the as a
- c. condition of participation in the CoAct Open Calls or does not fail to supply this information;

d. am not in one of the situations of exclusion, referred to in the above mentioned points 1a to 1f.

3. I certify that I:

- a. am committed to participate in the above mentioned project;
- b. have stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain activity throughout participation in the above mentioned project and to provide any counterpart funding necessary;
- c. have or will have the necessary resources as and when needed to carry out involvement in the above mentioned project.

4. I declare that I and other representatives of my organization will:

- a. ensure the quality, integrity and accuracy of research activities and outputs within the scope of the project;
- b. ensure informed consent of any and all volunteers taking part in the project, both data subjects (such as in the case of surveys) and project participants (such as citizen social scientists)
- c. take all steps to protect and ensure the confidentiality of all project participants;
- d. take all necessary steps to protect vulnerable groups who may participate within the project (particularly minors and those with a reduced capacity for consent);
- e. actively seek to encourage participation from underrepresented minority groups;
- f. comply with any and all legal requirements, both within the country or countries in which the project shall operate and at the European level, in particular the European Union General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679;
- g. take all reasonable steps to ensure project outputs are made openly available and accessible to the widest possible audience, where this does not infringe upon the rights and expectations of project participants, or contravene the legal requirements of the territories in which the project shall operate.

5. I declare that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, I am eligible to apply for the CoAct Open Calls and all the information I provided in the form is true.

Name

Signature

Date

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Annex 3: Review criteria

Idea	Relevance to the call	Does the proposal match the focus of the specific call it was submitted to? Does it include activities compatible with Citizen Social Science?
	Project design	Are the planned activities realistic given the proposed budget and time constraints? Does the scope and complexity of the project match the profiles of the project’s team?
Impact	Link to a broader agenda	Is the project linked to a broader agenda/programme carried out by the applicant? Does the project have a chance to continue beyond the length of the programme? Is the idea reusable by other organizations working on similar topics? Does the project present a participatory evaluation and impact assessment strategy?
	Documentation & Dissemination	Which documentation strategies are planned? Is there a commitment to publish the data and results? Where would the results of the projects be disseminated?
Ethics & Safety	Ethical considerations	Are there any ethical considerations relevant to the project, and if so how are they taken into account? Is there a clear commitment to data protection and anonymization where relevant? How does the applicant plan to ensure that their activities are as inclusive as possible?
	Health & Safety	If the project requires physical meetings, what processes are put in place to protect the health of participants in the contest of the Covid19 pandemic?

Annex 4: Negotiation documents

If you have passed the interview stage, you will be asked to submit a series of documents, as explained in this section.

1. Confirmation of affiliation

CoAct will ask you to confirm your affiliation through **a letter signed by the legal representative of your organization**. In a consortium, we will be carrying out this step for the leading organization.

2. Research project plan

During negotiations, the CoAct team will work with the research project to finalize a project plan for the ten months facilitation. Receiving any amount of funding from CoAct requires the applicant to **set and achieve** a set of milestones and/or KPIs. During this time, we will also provide more details on the workshops and other events, including the CoAct conference, which the projects will have to attend.

The project plan will include a (revised) budget. CoAct reserves the right to adjust the budget outlined by the applicant in the original submission based on feedback received during the interview. The final research project plan is going to be produced after CoAct the workshop.

3. Contract

Once a research project plan has been agreed, the applicant will be asked to sign a contract to formally join the CoAct facilitation. A preliminary template of the contract will be made available in due time.

The terms of the contract are the same for every research project accepted into the facilitation and cannot be negotiated.

The contract must be signed by the legal representative of the applicant. When projects are delivered by a consortium, the contract will be signed by the leading organization.

4. Bank account information

If negotiations are successful, CoAct will require bank account information of where to transfer the funding. Applicants will be asked to fill out the bank information template (see Annex 5). For consortia, we will distribute the funding to the leading entity.

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The bank information document will have to be signed (and, if applicable, stamped) by the legal representative of your organization. Use CAPITAL LETTERS and LATIN CHARACTERS when completing the form.

The form will also need to be signed by your bank to validate the information you have provided. Alternatively, you can provide a recent bank statement which confirms the details you have included in the form.

Please note that bank account information forms will not be accepted until they are signed by the organization representative.

5. Other documents

CoAct reserves the right to solicit any other document that allows us to assess the capacity and capability of the applicants to deliver the research project.

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Annex 5: Bank information

Name of organisation:

IBAN:

BIC:

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CoAct Open Calls - Application form

Welcome! Please fill this form to complete your application for the CoAct Gender Equality open call of your choice. We recommend reading the Applicant Guide and reviewing the questionnaire in advance by downloading the PDFs available at <https://coactproject.eu/opencalls>

Your answers will not be editable after clicking on the Submit button.

This form will be available until September 30th, 2021 11:59AM GMT, after which it will be deactivated. No application submitted after that deadline will be taken into account.

***Required**

Your choice of Open Call

1. Which Open Call do you want to apply for?

Mark only one oval.

- Gender Equality & Sustainable Cities and Communities for civic organisations in Berlin & Brandenburg area
- Gender Equality & Decent Work and Economic Growth for CSOs in Eastern Europe
- Gender Equality & Opportunities and Risks of Digitalization for International CSOs in the EU

About your organisation

2. Name of the organisation *

3. Are you registered as a non-profit organisation? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Not sure

4. Please share the city and country of registration of your organisation *

If your organisation has subsidiaries, please include the information of the subsidiary registered in the region of the Open Call

5. Please describe the main activities of your organisation *

6. Name of the organisation's contact person *

7. Email address used to contact you *

We will use this email to communicate the results of the selection process

8. If you are submitting this proposal on behalf of consortium, please list the name of the other member organisations

Your proposal

9. Please describe in a few sentences what your proposal aims to achieve *

10. Please explain the relevance of your proposal to gender equality issues and Citizen Social Science *

See the applicant guide for definitions

Project design

11. Please list the goals of your project *

12. Please list the activities planned in order to address these goals? *

13. What (technical, human) resources are necessary in order to enact those activities? *

14. Among resources listed previously, are there some that you will need to outsource? If so, which? *

Links to a broader agenda

This section looks at how your project fits your existing work, community and overall strategy.

15. How does the proposed project relate to the overall mission or programmatic agenda of your organisation/coalition? *

16. Will this project support the advancement of your organisation's overall agenda? if so, how? *

Documentation and dissemination

The CoAct Open Calls insist on the need to follow Open Science principles. Applications which do not include a dissemination strategy will not be considered.

17. How do you plan to document your project's progress? *

18. How and to which audiences do you plan to disseminate the results of your project? *

Sustainability

This section looks at how your project or its results can generate continued impact after the end of the grant

19. In what ways does your project or its results benefit the the communities you are part of? *

20. Are you planning to use software tools or resources to deliver your project? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Not sure

21. If yes, do you expect this software to be open source?

See here for a definition of Open Source: <https://opensource.com/resources/what-open-source>

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

22. If yes, will you develop the software yourself or do you plan to adapt existing tools?

Mark only one oval.

- We will develop the software
- We will reuse existing tools
- We will do both
- Other: _____

Ethical considerations

Ethical issues range from the collection of sensitive data such as race, religion, political opinions, to activities that present risks to the integrity of participants

23. Does your project present potential ethical issue? If so please list them *

COVID19 measures

24. Does your project present a health risk in the context of the COVID19 pandemic?
if so please state your plan to mitigate this risk. *
